

A NUMERICAL MODEL TO SIMULATE THE IMPACT RESPONSE OF FLAX-PP COMPOSITES

Swagata Dutta¹, Avishek Chanda², Md. Z. Rahman³, Raj Das⁴ and Debes Bhattacharyya⁵

¹ Centre for Advanced Composites Materials (CACM), Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Auckland, sdut182@aucklanduni.ac.nz

² Centre for Advanced Composites Materials (CACM), Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Auckland, acha553@aucklanduni.ac.nz

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology, mrah082@aucklanduni.ac.nz

⁴ Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Engineering, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia, raj.das@rmit.edu.au

⁵ Centre for Advanced Composites Materials (CACM), Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Auckland, d.bhattacharyya@auckland.ac.nz

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ABSTRACT

In this work, comprehensive experimental and numerical studies have been carried out to investigate the impact behaviour of flax fibre-reinforced polypropylene (PP) composites. A vacuum bagging process was used to manufacture the composite laminates. Afterwards, low-speed impact tests were carried out using a drop-weight impact test apparatus. A finite element model was developed employing a commercial finite element code ABAQUS, to simulate and predict the impact response. Both the experimental and numerical results were analysed on a single lamina scale. The results show reasonable agreements between the numerical model and the experimental results. The certain variations obtained were attributed to the higher amount of impact velocity (~ 2.2 m/s) used for the simulation, when compared to that of the experiment (~ 1.8 m/s). Apart from a few variations, the overall agreement is quite strong and the numerical predictions are significantly valid.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are widely used in different critical engineering applications. Engineered structures, manufactured from fibre reinforced composite materials, are often light-weight compared to conventional metal structures and these materials possess a range of properties, including both mechanical and multifunctional properties. Nevertheless, there are some serious limitations of composite materials. One of them is the susceptibility of the composite materials during localised impact, for instance, occurred by a dropped tool or debris from a runway. The composite materials are often subjected to impact loading in various applications, such as aerospace, marine, automotive and other applications. The most common failures of composite materials in the case of low-velocity impact are matrix cracking and delamination. Moreover, the presence of delaminations reduces the stiffness of the structure/laminate and may lead to catastrophic failure [1]. However, most of the studies focused on synthetic fibre reinforced composites and mostly dealing with the design of large military and civil aircraft.

Furthermore, there are significant differences in failure modes demonstrated by which the composite materials in response to an impact event when compared to their metal counterparts. In the past few years, many attempts have been undertaken to understand the impact response of composite materials [2-10]. In recent years sustainable composites made from natural materials are emerging and also finding applications in load bearing structures, which may be subjected to impact loading. The present paper thus focuses on the impact behaviour of natural composites. The conventional metals generally absorb energy leading to elastic or plastic deformation for low to intermediate incident energies. For high incident energies, the perforation may occur degrading the load bearing ability of the structure. On the other hand, composite materials frequently absorb energy creating large areas of

fracture. This is due to the extremely limited ability of these materials to undergo plastic deformation. The reduction in strength and stiffness is a by-product, and the ability to predict the post-impact load-bearing capability of these materials is very complex and extremely difficult to characterise [11].

Fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are comprised of three elements: the fibre, the matrix, and an interphase region. The global manner of the deformation process of FRP composites is largely governed by the chemical and mechanical properties of the elements. There have been several studies identifying the possible failure mechanisms in FRP composites [12-21]. The fibre, for instance, has the dominant role of carrying a significant portion of the applied load. A study conducted by Chamis et al. [22] suggested that the dominant energy absorbing mechanisms for composite materials are flexure and inter-laminar shear deformation. The authors also reported that the material's linear stress/strain diagram is a convenient tool for predicting the impact resistance of a composite material. In particular, the area under the stress-strain diagram is an indication of the energies absorbed during impact. However, a complete analysis should comprise energy associated with each failure modes occurring during impact.

On the other hand, the matrix plays a key role in keeping the fibres in place, align and stabilise the fibres, and also to assure stress transfer among fibres. Although the fibre is responsible for carrying most of the applied load, the role of the matrix is found critical to the overall behaviour of the composite materials. It was found that the load bearing capability of the composite material can reduce up to 50% depending on the extent of damage occurred in the matrix [23]. In addition, the mechanical performance of most of the composite materials is largely determined by the properties of the interphase region. There have been several attempts to increase the adhesion between the fibre and the matrix [24-29]. In general, an oxidative treatment is applied to the surface of the fibres to increase the bond. The extent of the treatment determines the impact resistance as well as the post-impact load carrying capability of the composites.

There have been many studies undertaken to understand the impact response of synthetic fibre-reinforced composites. However, according to the current literature, research on the impact resistance of plant fibre-reinforced composites is very limited. In particular, the simulation of impact response of plant fibre reinforced composites has been less explored. Therefore, in this paper, an attempt was made to comprehensively investigate the impact resistance of continuous flax fibre-reinforced polypropylene (PP) composites. Also, a numerical predictive model was developed to simulate the response of flax-PP composites under impact loading.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Sheets of PP random copolymer (MOPLEN RP241G) with a melt flow rate of 1.5 g/10 min determined by ISO 1,133 and a thickness of 0.38 mm were used as matrix material. The acquired sheets of PP are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sheets of Polypropylene as acquired from the manufacturer.

The PP was copolymerized with ethylene (typically 1–7% by weight). Lyondell Basell Industries produced the PP copolymer sheets and supplied by Field International Ltd., Auckland, New Zealand. The properties of PP are illustrated in Table 1 [30].

Properties type	PP
Grade	Moplen RP241G
Density (g/cm ³)	0.90
Tensile strength (MPa)	28
Flexural modulus (MPa)	1050
Notched Izod impact strength (23°C, KJ/m ²)	18
Falling weight impact strength (23°C, J)	12
Heat deflection temperature (°C)	68
Melt flow rate (230°C/2.16 kg) (g/10 min)	1.50
Melting temperature	145

Table 1: Mechanical and physical properties of the supplied polypropylene as per the datasheet

Unidirectional flax fabric (FlaxPly UD180) with a nominal specific weight of 180 g/m² and density of 1.42 g/cm³ was used as reinforcement. Lineo, Meulebeke, Belgium supplied the flax fabric (42.5 yarns/cm [warp] and three yarns/cm [weft]). The weight distribution of flax fabric in the warp and weft directions was 95.5% and 4.5%, respectively. The role of weft (or fill) yarns is to keep the warp yarns in place.

2.2 Manufacturing the composites

The flax-PP composite samples were manufactured by the vacuum bagging technique. The technique uses atmospheric pressure to hold the laminate in place during the cure cycle. At first, the flax fabrics were dried for 24 h at 70°C in a vacuum dryer (Squaroid duo-vac vacuum oven) to reduce the moisture content. Dry flax fabrics and PP sheets were interleaved in a hand lay-up process and placed on an aluminium plate to fabricate unidirectional composite laminates. A peel ply was then used to separate the breather from the laminate, and the breather was employed to ensure all the air inside the vacuum bag could be drawn into a vacuum port. After sealing the material stack, the air was evacuated from inside the vacuum bag using a vacuum pump. The mould was subsequently placed inside the Elecfurn (FAC 100) oven and heated to a temperature of 190°C for one h. After this, the mould was cooled to a room temperature of 25°C. The size of the panels was nominally 600 × 500 mm, with a target thickness of 3 mm, and target fibre volume fraction of 0.31. Corresponding to the fibre composition, samples with a fibre orientation of 0° were cut from the panels using an automatic saw.

2.3 Impact test

Drop weight impact tests were carried out by an Imatek IM10T-20 Drop Weight Impact Tester as per the ASTM D7136-15 standard. A typical load-deflection diagram, for any standard drop-weight impact test, is given in Figure 2. The maximum amount of force, any sample can withstand is denoted by F_m in the graph and the amount of energy required by the sample to reach this point is denoted as E_i , which is also known as the energy required for initiating cracks. Once the cracks are initiated, the sample experiences propagation of cracks with reduced force and E_p represents the energy required to complete the crack propagation process. The post-perforation frictional section is represented by the horizontal section at the end, however, this section needs to be removed in order to estimate the true amount of energy absorbed. The removal is carried out by extending the line, representing the propagation phase, to an estimated point, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Deflection history of the force for a typical drop-weight impact test

Laminates of size 150 x 100 mm were placed on a rectangular fixture. The fixture contains a rectangular aperture of dimension of 125 x 75 mm at the centre. The tests were performed using a steel hemispherical tip striker with a diameter of 16 ± 0.1 mm and a mass of 1.22 kg. The striker was attached to a titanium impactor (mass of 8.53 kg). The specimens were tested at impact energy of 35 J which was sufficient to perforate the specimens. The impactor was released from a constant height of 209 mm which produces an impact velocity of 2.02 m/s during the impact event. Ten specimens were considered for each composite sample, and the mean results were reported.

Figure 2: Illustration of the drop-weight impact test setup

2.4 Numerical Simulation

The numerical modelling was carried out following the ASTM D7136/D7136M-15 standard to replicate the experimental test configuration. A commercially available finite element (FE) code, ABAQUS explicit was used to simulate the impact response of the flax-PP laminates. To reduce computational time, symmetry condition of laminate was used and one-fourth part of the entire assembly was modelled. Therefore, the size of the composite lamina was 62.5 mm x 37.5 mm x 0.3 mm. Similarly, one-fourth part of the impactor was modelled. The entire assembly of the simulation is shown in Figure 3. The impactor was modelled as a rigid body with a user-defined initial mass determined from experiment. Moreover, engineering elastic properties of the composite laminates were predicted using a periodic microstructure model [31]. Hashin's damage criteria were incorporated into composite material property according to the present literature [32]. In ABAQUS, a dynamic/explicit step was conducted. The simulation was performed for ten milliseconds. Furthermore, the interaction between the impactor and the lamina was modelled assigning both tangential and normal behaviour. In the case of tangential behaviour, an isotropic frictional coefficient was specified. On the other hand, normal behaviour was modelled as hard contact. Appropriate boundary conditions were given to the laminates to define the complete impact phenomena. Likewise, the impactor was also specified with appropriate velocity boundary conditions obtained from the experiment. Additionally, the velocity-time history obtained from the experiment was also incorporated in the simulation of the impactor. A mesh sensitivity study was conducted to element any effect of mesh size on the simulation results. An 8-node quadrilateral in-plane general purpose continuum shell with reduced integration and hourglass control (stiffness) was used as mesh element for the composite laminates. To simulate material impact response, the maximum degradation of the mesh elements was also specified.

Figure 3: Drop-weight impact test simulation

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 2 shows the load and energy absorbed obtained from the drop-weight impact test.

Fibre orientation (θ)	Peak load (kN)	Initiation energy (J)	Propagation energy (J)	Total absorbed energy (J)
0°	0.72 ± 0.10	12.46 ± 0.44	12.80 ± 0.46	25.26 ± 0.84

Table 1: Drop weight impact test results of flax/PP composites for a volume fraction of 0.31 V_f

It can be observed that, for the current concentration of flax-PP, the maximum amount of energy is dissipated during the crack propagation phase, which is marginally higher than that of the crack

initiation phase. Therefore, the results indicate that the amount of energy absorption is lower in the initiation phase, when compared to the propagation phase. The peak load, that the composite sample can withstand, was observed to be about 0.72 kN. In addition, the total amount of energy absorbed by the composite sample during the impact event, including all the phases, was calculated to be about 25.26 J. Therefore, it was observed that the sample absorbs more energy during the propagation while withstanding lesser load.

Figure 4: Drop weight impact fracture samples: Impacted surface (left) and non-impacted surface (right)

The variation in the size of the cracks and damaged areas of the sample is shown in Figure 5. The composite sample encounters various failure modes upon impact loading. The impact failure observed on the composite samples is a complete penetration. The damage propagates along the fibre/matrix interfaces as the interfaces are weak, which causes debonding. The failure of the fibres and matrix is noticeable on the surfaces. Furthermore, an extensive whitening phenomenon is observed on the surface of the composite along with the heavy deformation. This phenomenon is caused by micro-void nucleation and growth in the polymer [33]. Impact damage in the samples is mainly due to matrix deformation and cracking, failure and fracture of the fibres, fibre/matrix debonding, and fibre pull-out. A centrally displaced zone and surface buckling were also observed at the damaged regions. Numerical simulation was carried out, which was validated based on the experimental results. The simulated responses were recorded and analysed based on the peak load, energy absorbed, impact velocity and displacement. Figure 7a) represents the Hashin's failure criteria, which helps in understanding the various failure modes, by using multiple stress components. It can be observed that the maximum stress is experienced by the samples at the laminate joints, proving that the possibility of delamination is very high. It can also be inferred, from the large displacement of the sample, at the point of impact, that the impactor has gone through the laminate from the impacting side to the non-impacting side.

Figure 5: Simulation of viscous and frictional dissipation energy vs. time curves for the flax-PP composite samples

Figure 7b) helps in graphically representing the final structure of the simulated sample, where it can be clearly observed that the impactor has completely penetrated the sample. Another significant observation is the amount of stress concentration on the laminate bonds and the delamination experienced by the sample. The delamination can be observed to propagate from the bottom lamina and therefore, the stress concentration is also maximum at the bonding face of the bottom lamina.

The comparison between the time and displacement history of experimental observations and numerical predictions are presented in Figure 8. The force-time history curves of the flax-PP composite laminates are presented in Figure 8a). It is to be noted that the overall response and contact times are well predicted by the numerical simulation. In contrast, the damage threshold, the point where a considerable change in the stiffness of the composite occurs, is slightly over-predicted in the simulation. Also, the time of impact and the initial linear part of the force-time curve have been accurately predicted by the simulation. However, the contact duration is slightly under-predicted. The maximum impact force, F_m is reasonably well predicted, however, the simulated force-time curve drops quite abruptly after attaining the peak form (F_m) leading to reduced contact time (~ 8 ms).

In contrast, the experimental force-time curve remained steady during the entire period. The drop in the simulated force-time curve is due to the damage initiated during the impact process. The combination of crack initiation, and propagation contributed to the overall failure mechanisms. The energy was absorbed until the composite samples were perforated completely. Moreover, the force-displacement curves as presented in Figure 8b) show similar trends. An important difference is a sudden drop in the simulated force-displacement curve indicating less deformation (~ 15 mm) as compared to the experimental findings (~ 20 mm). The reason can be attributed to the higher impactor velocity during the entire period of simulation (Figure 8c)). The initial impactor velocity in the simulation is ~ 2.2 m/s whereas it is ~ 1.8 m/s in experiments. The higher impactor velocity not only increased the maximum impact force (F_m) but also shortened the contact duration. Figure 8d) presents the experimental and simulated curves of the absorbed energy during the impact event. It can be seen that the simulated curve is in good agreement with the experimental curve until four milliseconds. However, afterwards, the simulated energy-time curve show significantly higher values as compared to the experimental one. This may be partly due to the material properties that were used in the simulation are predicted by an analytical model which may incur possible discrepancies.

Figure 6: Graphical representation of the simulated sample showing a) Hashin's failure criteria and b) possible delamination

Figure 7: Experimental and numerical results time histories of a) force-time history, b) displacement-force history c) impact velocity-time history and d) energy-time history and of the Flax-PP composite samples

Another possible reason is the higher impactor velocity associated with the simulation during the entire period. The simulation was able to predict the dissipated energies during the impact event (Figure 6) as can be observed from the figure that the significant part of the dissipated energy was viscous dissipation energy during the entire period. However, frictional dissipation comes into play after ~ 4 milliseconds.

4 CONCLUSION

The impact behaviour of flax-PP natural fibre composite was investigated by low-speed impact tests and numerical modelling under drop weight impact load. The impact responses from the finite element model show reasonably good agreement with the experimentally measured response. The test results help in predicting the behaviour of flax-PP composites during impact and the numerical results help in establishing that the method used can predict the impact strength of plant fibre composites without using experiments. The amount of peak load sustained by the unidirectional flax-PP composite shows the potential of increasing the load capacity of these composites by changing the fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction. The finite element based numerical model can be effectively used in predicting the low-velocity impact behaviour of natural fibre composites.

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